

Environmental pollution from mobile chemicals leads to degradation of ecosystem services such as water purification, nutrient cycling, and crop yields. It also leads to a loss of biodiversity and a reduction in quality of life. Exposure to chemical pollutants occurs through the food chain, drinking water, skin contact, and inhalation of airborne particles.

SCENARIOS provides a complete set of sustainable solutions to protect human health, the environment, and natural resources from persistent and mobile chemicals, and PFAS.

SCENARIOS's approach and technologies will be self-sustainable, (near) net-zero energy and will smoothly integrate in the circular economy concept of EU countries and worldwide.

<https://scenarios-project.eu/>

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